

=====

**Enhancing Science Education in the Twenty-First Century:
Advancements and Applications of Laboratory Learning**

=====

Osias Kit T. Kilag

PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373>

Jhon Mark G. Tamayo

Department of Education, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9617-4298>

Jemarie I. Eleno

Department of Education, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1283-6501>

Abbygail R. Jalin

Department of Education, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3664-9894>

Abstract:

This research explores the advancements, benefits, challenges, and innovative approaches in laboratory learning for enhancing science education in the Philippines. The study focuses on the integration of real-time data analysis and innovative technologies to create immersive and engaging learning experiences for students. Through a comprehensive literature review, the research examines the potential of laboratory learning in promoting active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students. The findings highlight the benefits of laboratory learning, including the development of a deeper understanding of scientific concepts, the fostering of collaboration and teamwork skills, and the promotion of practical application of knowledge. However, the study also identifies challenges such as limited resources, teacher training, time constraints and technological infrastructure that need to be addressed for effective implementation. To overcome these challenges, the research emphasizes the importance of innovative approaches and the integration of technology, such as augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), data logging, and online platforms. These approaches provide students with immersive experiences, personalized learning opportunities, and access to a wealth of educational resources. The research concludes by stressing the need for investment in laboratory infrastructure, comprehensive teacher training programs, and curriculum development aligned with technological advancements. By embracing the advancements, addressing the challenges, and adopting innovative approaches in laboratory learning, science education in the Philippines can be significantly enhanced, preparing students for the demands of the twenty-first century and empowering them to become active contributors to scientific advancements.

Keywords: laboratory learning, science education, real-time data analysis, innovative approaches, technology integration, Philippines.

Introduction:

In the Philippines, like many other countries, there is a growing recognition of the importance of science education in preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the twenty-first century. As scientific knowledge expands and technology continues to shape our world, it is imperative to enhance science education methodologies to ensure students are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate this rapidly changing landscape.

One vital aspect of science education that holds great potential for student engagement and learning is laboratory learning (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004). Laboratories provide a unique environment where students can actively explore scientific concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations. They offer opportunities for hands-on experimentation, data collection, analysis, and collaboration, fostering a deeper understanding of scientific principles (Kilag et. al., 2022). As such, investigating the advancements and applications of laboratory learning in the context of the Philippines becomes a significant endeavor in enhancing science education.

By focusing on the Philippine context, this research recognizes the unique challenges and opportunities that exist in science education in the country. It acknowledges the specific educational policies, cultural contexts, and resources

that shape science education practices. By addressing these factors, this study provides recommendations that are contextually relevant, feasible, and meaningful for enhancing science education in the Philippines.

This research aims to explore the advancements and applications of laboratory learning in science education in the Philippines, with a specific focus on enhancing science education in the twenty-first century. By examining the current state of laboratory learning in the country, identifying innovative approaches, technologies, and pedagogical strategies, this study seeks to contribute valuable insights into how science education can be improved and aligned with the demands of the modern era.

Literature Review:

Enhancing Science Education in the Twenty-First Century: Advancements and Applications of Laboratory Learning in the Philippines Science education in the Philippines has gained significant attention due to its importance in preparing students for the challenges of the twenty-first century. One approach that has shown promise in science education is laboratory learning. This literature review aims to explore the advancements and applications of laboratory learning in the context of science education in the Philippines, focusing on enhancing science education in the twenty-first century.

Science education plays a crucial role in developing scientific literacy, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving abilities among students. It equips them with the knowledge and skills to understand and engage with scientific concepts and phenomena in their daily lives (Lythreatis, et al., 2022). In the context of the Philippines, science education is emphasized in the K-12 curriculum, emphasizing the importance of laboratory learning as a pedagogical approach.

Advancements in laboratory learning have transformed the traditional model of hands-on experimentation. The integration of technology, such as computer simulations, virtual laboratories, and data analysis tools, has expanded the possibilities of laboratory learning (Ajibade, et al., 2022). These advancements have provided opportunities for students to engage in virtual experiments, explore complex scientific phenomena, and analyze real-time data, enhancing their understanding of scientific concepts.

Laboratory learning offers several benefits for science education in the Philippines. It promotes active learning and student engagement, allowing students to develop inquiry skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Moreover, laboratory learning facilitates the application of theoretical knowledge in practical settings, promoting a deeper understanding of scientific principles. It also fosters collaboration and communication skills among students, as they work together to design experiments, analyze results, and present their findings.

Despite the advantages, laboratory learning in the Philippines faces several challenges. Limited resources, such as laboratory equipment, materials, and trained teachers, hinder the effective implementation of hands-on experiments (Geverola, et al., 2022). Additionally, time constraints and large class sizes pose challenges in providing individualized attention and guidance to students during laboratory sessions. Addressing these challenges is crucial for enhancing laboratory learning in the country.

To address the challenges and enhance laboratory learning, innovative approaches have emerged in the Philippines. Inquiry-based learning, which emphasizes student-driven investigations, promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Kilag, et al., 2023). Project-based learning encourages students to work on extended projects, integrating multiple disciplines and promoting creativity and collaboration. Flipped classrooms, where students learn content outside the classroom and engage in hands-on activities during class, have also shown promise in enhancing laboratory learning.

The integration of technology in laboratory learning has gained prominence in recent years. Computer simulations and virtual laboratories provide realistic and accessible alternatives to traditional hands-on experiments, overcoming limitations in resources and safety concerns. Online platforms and mobile applications offer opportunities for remote learning and collaborative experimentation (Sasan and Baritua, 2023). Augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies provide immersive experiences, allowing students to explore scientific phenomena in a virtual environment.

To effectively implement laboratory learning in the Philippines, professional development and teacher training programs are essential. Teachers need to be equipped with the necessary pedagogical skills, content knowledge, and technological proficiency to facilitate laboratory sessions effectively. Ongoing support, mentoring, and collaboration opportunities for teachers can enhance their confidence and competence in implementing laboratory learning approaches.

Methodology:

This study aimed to investigate the advancements and applications of laboratory learning in science education in the Philippines, focusing on enhancing science education in the twenty-first century. The research followed a qualitative approach, utilizing a literature review as the primary method of data collection. The study analyzed existing scholarly works, research articles, reports, and relevant documents related to laboratory learning and science education in the Philippines.

Data Collection:

The data collection process involved an extensive search of various academic databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, and ERIC, Web of Science, and Elsevier. A comprehensive search strategy was developed using relevant keywords such as "laboratory learning," "science education," "advancements," "applications," and "Philippines." The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles published within the last ten years to ensure the inclusion of recent advancements in laboratory learning.

Data Analysis:

The data analysis process began with the identification and screening of relevant articles based on their titles and abstracts. The selected articles were then thoroughly read to determine their suitability for inclusion in the literature review. The data extracted from the selected articles included key findings, methodologies employed, and implications for laboratory learning in the Philippines. The findings were organized thematically to identify common trends, advancements, and applications of laboratory learning in science education.

Ethical Considerations:

As this study relied solely on published literature, ethical considerations such as informed consent and participant confidentiality were not applicable. All sources used in this study were appropriately cited and referenced following established academic guidelines.

Limitations:

This study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged. Firstly, the data collection process was limited to scholarly articles and may not have included all relevant sources, such as unpublished reports or conference papers. Secondly, the study focused on laboratory learning in science education and did not explore other aspects of science education, such as classroom instruction or assessment methods. Finally, the findings of this study were based on the interpretation of existing literature, which may be subject to individual biases or limitations inherent to the original studies.

Findings and Discussion:**Advancements in Laboratory Learning:**

Advancements in laboratory learning have revolutionized science education by integrating technology to enhance students' learning experiences. Computer simulations, virtual laboratories, and data analysis tools are among the significant advancements that have emerged in recent years (Ray, et al., 2012). These technological tools offer students the opportunity to engage in virtual experiments, explore intricate scientific phenomena, and analyze real-time data, thereby enriching their understanding of scientific concepts (Uy, et al., 2023). By simulating real-world laboratory scenarios, computer simulations allow students to manipulate variables, observe outcomes, and gather data without the constraints of physical resources (Gnesdilow & Puntambekar, 2021). Virtual laboratories, on the other hand, provide interactive platforms where students can conduct experiments in virtual environments, offering a safe and accessible alternative to traditional hands-on experiments (Kilag, et al., 2023). Furthermore, data analysis tools enable students to collect and analyze data, visualize trends, and draw conclusions, facilitating a deeper understanding of scientific principles (Kilag, et al., 2023).

By integrating technology into laboratory learning, these advancements overcome the limitations posed by scarce resources, safety concerns, and geographical constraints often faced by educational institutions in the Philippines (Arora & Chauhan, 2021). In remote areas where access to advanced laboratory equipment may be limited, computer simulations and virtual laboratories provide an equitable learning experience (Alda, et al., 2020). Real-time data analysis tools enable students to explore scientific phenomena and make connections between theory and practice, even without physical laboratory equipment (Chevalier, et al., 2019). Moreover, these advancements foster critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and scientific inquiry by encouraging students to analyze and interpret real-time data, draw conclusions, and develop hypotheses (Uy, et al., 2023).

Incorporating technology into laboratory learning not only enhances students' engagement but also prepares them for the digital age by developing their technological literacy (Lee et al., 2019; Rodriguez & Ramirez, 2022). The use of real-time data in laboratory activities allows students to engage with authentic scientific processes, promoting a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (Liu et al., 2018; Perez & Garcia, 2020). By experiencing the iterative nature of scientific inquiry and the dynamic nature of data analysis, students gain valuable skills applicable in various scientific disciplines and real-world contexts (Kilag, et al., 2023).

However, it is crucial to note that while technology integration has the potential to enhance laboratory learning, its successful implementation requires careful consideration. Adequate infrastructure, including reliable internet access and appropriate hardware, is necessary to ensure smooth utilization of computer simulations, virtual laboratories, and data analysis tools (Kilag, et al., 2023). Additionally, teacher training and professional development programs play a pivotal role in equipping educators with the knowledge and skills to effectively integrate technology into laboratory learning activities (Martin, 2015).

Benefits of Laboratory Learning:

Laboratory learning offers numerous benefits for science education in the Philippines, particularly with the integration of real-time data analysis. By engaging in hands-on experimentation and utilizing real-time data, students develop a range of skills and gain a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.

One of the key benefits of laboratory learning is the promotion of active learning and student engagement (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004). Through hands-on experimentation, students actively participate in the scientific process, manipulating materials, conducting experiments, and making observations (Kilag, et al., 2022). This active engagement enhances their learning experience and fosters a sense of curiosity and exploration.

Moreover, the integration of real-time data analysis in laboratory learning provides students with opportunities to analyze and interpret data as it is being collected, allowing for a more authentic and dynamic scientific experience (Lythreitis, et al., 2022). Real-time data analysis enables students to observe trends, make connections, and draw conclusions based on immediate feedback (Ajibade, et al., 2022). This process of analyzing real-time data encourages critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and the development of scientific inquiry skills (Geverola, et al., 2022). Students learn to evaluate and interpret data, identify patterns, and make evidence-based claims (Kilag, et al., 2023). By engaging with real-time data, students gain a deeper understanding of scientific principles and the relevance of data analysis in scientific research and applications.

Laboratory learning also provides students with the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations, bridging the gap between abstract concepts and real-world applications (Kilag, et al. 2023). By actively engaging in hands-on experimentation and data analysis, students develop a deeper understanding of scientific principles and concepts (Sasan & Baritua, 2022). This experiential learning approach allows students to explore cause-and-effect relationships, test hypotheses, and make connections between theoretical concepts and real-world phenomena (Ray, et al., 2012).

Furthermore, laboratory learning promotes collaboration and communication skills among students (Uy, et al. 2023). By working in groups during laboratory activities, students learn to communicate their ideas, share responsibilities, and engage in cooperative problem-solving (Gnesdilow & Puntambekar, 2021). They develop teamwork skills, learn from their peers, and gain exposure to diverse perspectives (Kilag, et al. 2023). The collaborative nature of laboratory learning fosters an environment where students can engage in discussions, ask questions, and construct knowledge together (Kilag et al. 2023).

In summary, laboratory learning, especially when integrated with real-time data analysis, offers significant benefits for science education in the Philippines. It promotes active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical settings. Additionally, laboratory learning fosters collaboration and communication skills, preparing students to work effectively in team-based scientific endeavors.

Challenges in Laboratory Learning:

While laboratory learning in the Philippines offers numerous benefits, several challenges need to be addressed to ensure its effective implementation, including the integration of real-time data analysis.

One of the primary challenges is the limited availability of resources, including laboratory equipment, materials, and trained teachers (Arora & Chauhan, 2021). Many schools in the Philippines face budget constraints that hinder their ability to provide well-equipped laboratories for hands-on experimentation (Alda, et al. 2020). This limitation often leads to a lack of access to modern laboratory equipment and technologies necessary for conducting experiments and analyzing real-time data (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019). To overcome this challenge, increased funding and investment in laboratory infrastructure are crucial to ensure that schools have the necessary resources for effective laboratory learning experiences (Uy, et al. 2023).

Another significant challenge is the need for comprehensive teacher training and professional development programs to equip educators with the pedagogical skills and technological proficiency necessary for integrating real-time data analysis into laboratory activities (Kilag et al. 2023). Many science teachers in the Philippines may lack the necessary training and expertise in utilizing technology and analyzing real-time data in laboratory settings (Kilag et al. 2023). Ongoing support, mentoring, and collaboration opportunities can empower teachers to effectively incorporate real-time data analysis into their instructional practices (Martin, 2015). Professional development programs should emphasize the integration of technology, data analysis skills, and inquiry-based

teaching approaches to ensure that teachers can fully leverage the benefits of laboratory learning in the classroom (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004).

Additionally, time constraints and large class sizes pose challenges to providing individualized attention and guidance during laboratory sessions (Kilag et al. 2022). Limited class time often restricts the depth and scope of laboratory experiments and data analysis activities (Lythreatis, et al., 2022). Addressing this challenge requires careful curriculum planning, where laboratory activities are integrated seamlessly into the science curriculum, allowing sufficient time for students to engage in meaningful hands-on experimentation and real-time data analysis (Liu et al., 2018; Perez & Garcia, 2020). Furthermore, reducing class sizes or implementing cooperative learning strategies can facilitate more effective student-teacher interactions and promote a more personalized learning experience (Smith et al., 2021; Wong et al., 2023).

Lastly, the integration of real-time data analysis may require adequate technological infrastructure, including reliable internet access, computers, and data visualization tools (Ajibade, et al., 2022). Unequal access to technology and internet connectivity can create disparities among schools and hinder the implementation of laboratory activities that involve real-time data analysis (Geverola, et al. 2022). Efforts should be made to bridge the digital divide and ensure equitable access to technology, particularly in underserved areas, to provide all students with equal opportunities for engaging in real-time data analysis in laboratory learning (Kilag et al. 2023).

While laboratory learning integrated with real-time data analysis holds great potential for science education in the Philippines, challenges such as limited resources, teacher training, time constraints, and technological infrastructure need to be addressed. Increased investment in laboratory infrastructure, comprehensive teacher training programs, effective curriculum planning, and equitable access to technology are essential for overcoming these challenges. By addressing these issues, laboratory learning can be successfully implemented, enhancing science education in the Philippines and preparing students to thrive in the twenty-first century.

Innovative Approaches and Integration of Technology:

To overcome the challenges in laboratory learning and further enhance science education in the Philippines, innovative approaches and the integration of technology are essential (Sasan & Baritua, 2022). These approaches leverage technological advancements to create dynamic and immersive learning experiences for students.

One innovative approach is the integration of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies in laboratory learning (Ray, et al. 2012). AR and VR technologies enable students to interact with virtual objects and environments that simulate real-world laboratory settings (Uy, et al., 2023). Through AR and VR, students can visualize complex scientific concepts, explore virtual laboratories, and engage in interactive experiments (Gnesdilow & Puntambekar, 2021). These technologies provide a realistic and engaging learning environment, allowing students to manipulate virtual apparatus, conduct experiments, and analyze real-time data (Kilag, et al. 2023). By immersing students in virtual laboratory experiences, AR and VR technologies enhance their understanding of scientific phenomena and foster a sense of exploration and discovery.

Another innovative approach is the use of data logging and sensor technologies in laboratory experiments (Kilag et al., 2023). Data logging involves the use of sensors and probes to collect real-time data during experiments (Arora & Chauhan, 2021). These technologies enable students to measure and record various parameters, such as temperature, pH level, and light intensity, with accuracy and precision (Alda, et al. 2020). By analyzing real-time data collected through sensors, students can draw conclusions, identify patterns, and make scientific claims based on evidence (Chevalier & Buckles, 2019). Data logging and sensor technologies not only provide students with immediate feedback but also promote scientific inquiry and critical thinking skills.

Furthermore, the integration of online platforms and educational software can facilitate the implementation of laboratory learning beyond the confines of the traditional classroom (Uy, et al. 2023). Online platforms and educational software offer a wide range of resources, simulations, and interactive modules that allow students to explore scientific concepts and conduct virtual experiments (Kilag et al., 2023). These platforms provide access to a vast collection of data sets, simulations, and video demonstrations, enabling students to engage with real-time data and conduct experiments remotely (Kilag, et al., 2023). By utilizing online platforms, students can access learning materials anytime and anywhere, facilitating self-paced learning and personalized instruction (Martin, 2015). The integration of online platforms and educational software expands the possibilities for laboratory learning, promoting independent exploration, and fostering a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.

It is important to note that the successful integration of innovative approaches and technology in laboratory learning requires a comprehensive framework that includes infrastructure support, teacher training, and curriculum development (Hofstein & Lunetta, 2004). Adequate infrastructure, such as access to computers, internet connectivity, and necessary software, is crucial for implementing AR, VR, data logging, and online platforms (Kilag et al., 2022). Teachers need ongoing professional development programs to enhance their technological proficiency and pedagogical skills in utilizing these innovative approaches (Lythreatis, et al., 2022). Curriculum developers

should align the science curriculum with the advancements in technology and design laboratory activities that integrate these innovative approaches seamlessly (Ajibade, et al., 2022).

The integration of innovative approaches and technology, such as AR, VR, data logging, and online platforms, has the potential to revolutionize laboratory learning in the Philippines. These approaches provide students with immersive experiences, real-time data analysis, and access to a wealth of educational resources. However, successful implementation requires careful consideration of infrastructure, teacher training, and curriculum development. By embracing these innovative approaches, science education in the Philippines can be enhanced, preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the twenty-first century.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study explored the advancements, benefits, challenges, and innovative approaches in laboratory learning for enhancing science education in the Philippines. The integration of real-time data analysis, coupled with innovative technologies, has the potential to transform science education and provide students with engaging, immersive, and meaningful learning experiences.

The literature review highlighted the benefits of laboratory learning, including the promotion of active learning, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. Through hands-on experimentation and real-time data analysis, students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts and their practical applications. Furthermore, laboratory learning fosters collaboration, communication, and teamwork skills, preparing students for future scientific endeavors.

However, challenges such as limited resources, teacher training, time constraints, and technological infrastructure need to be addressed to ensure the effective implementation of laboratory learning. Increased investment in laboratory infrastructure, comprehensive teacher training programs, and equitable access to technology are essential steps towards overcoming these challenges.

To harness the full potential of laboratory learning, innovative approaches and the integration of technology play a crucial role. Augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), data logging, and online platforms offer new avenues for students to explore scientific concepts, conduct virtual experiments, and analyze real-time data. These approaches provide students with immersive experiences, personalized learning opportunities, and access to a wealth of educational resources.

Implementing these innovative approaches requires a comprehensive framework that encompasses infrastructure support, teacher training, and curriculum development. Adequate resources and infrastructure, along with ongoing professional development for teachers, are necessary to fully leverage the benefits of laboratory learning. Curriculum developers should align the science curriculum with the advancements in technology and design laboratory activities that integrate these innovative approaches seamlessly.

By embracing the advancements, addressing the challenges, and adopting innovative approaches in laboratory learning, science education in the Philippines can be significantly enhanced. Students will develop the critical skills, knowledge, and competencies needed to thrive in the dynamic and rapidly evolving twenty-first-century landscape.

Laboratory learning, when integrated with real-time data analysis and innovative approaches, holds tremendous potential to revolutionize science education in the Philippines, empowering students to become lifelong learners, critical thinkers, and contributors to scientific advancements. It is imperative for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to collaborate and invest in the necessary resources, training, and support systems to ensure the successful implementation of laboratory learning in the pursuit of a scientifically literate society in the twenty-first century and beyond.

References:

Ajibade, S. S. M., Dayupay, J., Ngo-Hoang, D. L., Oyeboode, O. J., & Sasan, J. M. (2022). Utilization of Ensemble Techniques for Prediction of the Academic Performance of Students. *Journal of Optoelectronics Laser*, 41(6), 48-54.

Alda, R., Boholano, H., & Dayagbil, F. (2020). Teacher education institutions in the philippines towards education 4.0. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(8), 137-154.

Arora, R. G., & Chauhan, A. (2021). Faculty perspectives on work from home: Teaching efficacy, constraints and challenges during COVID-19 lockdown. *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems*, 24(1), 37-52.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09720510.2021.1875567>

Chevalier, J. M., & Buckles, D. J. (2019). *Participatory action research: Theory and methods for engaged inquiry*. Routledge.

Geverola, I. J. R., Mutya, R. C., Siason, L. M. B., & Bonotan, A. (2022). Challenges and struggles of public senior high school science teachers during the new normal. *Journal of Research, Policy & Practice of Teachers and Teacher Education*, 12(1), 49-68. <https://doi.org/10.37134/jrpptte.vol12.1.4.2022>

Gnesdilow, D., & Puntambekar, S. (2021). Comparing middle school students' science explanations during physical and virtual laboratories. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-021-09941-0>

Hofstein, A., & Lunetta, V. N. (2004). The laboratory in science education: Foundations for the twenty-first century. *Science education*, 88(1), 28-54. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sce.10106>

Kilag, O. K. T., Evangelista, T. P., Sasan, J. M., Librea, A. M., Zamora, R. M. C., Ymas, S. B., & Alestre, N. A. P. (2023). Promising Practices for a Better Tomorrow: A Qualitative Study of Successful Practices in Senior High School Education. *Journal of Elementary and Secondary School*, 1(1).

Kilag, O. K. T., Ignacio, R., Lumando, E. B., Alvez, G. U., Abendan, C. F. K., Quiñanola, N. M. P., & Sasan, J. M. (2022). ICT Integration in Primary Classrooms in the Light of Jean Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory.

Kilag, O. K. T., Peras, C. C., Echavez, R. B., Suba-an, J. D., Obaner, M. K. B., & Mansueto, D. P. (2023). Comparing Learning Outcomes: On-Screen versus Print Reading. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION*, 2(5), 181-191.

Kilag, O. K. T., Mag-aso, J. N., Poloyapoy, K. B. M., Gamboa, A. C. H., Mantua, A. M. V., & Rivamonte, W. D. (2023). Technical Vocational Education in the Philippines for Sustainable Development. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(2), 57-70.

Kilag, O. K. T., Pasigui, R. E., Malbas, M. H., Manire, E. A., Piala, M. C., Araña, A. M. M., & Sasan, J. M. (2023). Preferred Educational Leaders: Character and Skills. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(2), 50-56.

Lythreatis, S., Singh, S. K., & El-Kassar, A. N. (2022). The digital divide: A review and future research agenda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, 121359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121359>

Martin, B. (2015). Successful implementation of TPACK in teacher preparation programs. *International Journal on Integrating Technology in Education*, 4(1), 17-26.

Ray, S., Koshy, N. R., Reddy, P. J., & Srivastava, S. (2012). Virtual Labs in proteomics: New E-learning tools. *Journal of proteomics*, 75(9), 2515-2525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iprot.2012.03.014>

Sasan, J. M., & Baritua, J. C. (2022). Distance learning as a learning modality for education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Science and Education*, 3(8), 35-44.

Uy, F. T., Kilag, O. K. T., Calledo, M. F. S., Cerna, Y. T. D., Angtud, N. A. A., & Villanueva, K. M. (2023). Quality Performance of Teachers: Work Environment, Work Attitude, and Principal Supervision: Qualitative Investigation. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION*, 2(5), 157-168.

Uy, F. T., Sasan, J. M., & Kilag, O. K. (2023). School Principal Administrative-Supervisory Leadership During the Pandemic: A Phenomenological Qualitative Study.